

SPEAC – Sharing Perspectives on Effective Academic Communication

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2. Background and Rationale

Writing scientific articles can be a struggle for academic students and writers (Lee, A & Kamler, B, 2008). Although it is the method for knowledge translation in academia, there is surprisingly little academic literature (or other sources of information) on the topic. One study

on how to achieve expert levels, does touch upon academic performance, but only briefly and not supported by systematic data collection within highly productive researchers (Ericsson, K, Krampe, R, Tesch-Roemer, C , 1993).

The aim of this project is to investigate the methods used by the most productive researchers, and possibly identify aspects that can later on be used for quantitative data collections on the topic.

While the aim and results of this research project is highly interesting for a wide range of academic students and writers, the research process itself is relatively slow. And at the same time, particularly qualitative research is subject to biases from the researcher. Consequently, in this project, the data will be distributed throughout the data collection process, through a podcast. Podcast is on demand listening, and is available through native apps on all smartphones, and through online access. You decide to subscribe to a certain channel, and whenever new episodes are presented, they'll be automatically presented to you (Mchugh, S, 2016). This means that listeners to the channel will be able to learn and draw their own conclusions from the interviews with highly productive researchers during the research process. Without delay, and with a minimum of researcher bias.

3. Objectives and Research Questions

The objectives of this project are to determine the characteristics of highly productive researchers, including:

- What strategies do highly productive researchers employ when writing scientific articles?
- What are the common challenges faced by researchers, and how do they overcome them?

4. Methodology

4.1 Study Design

This project will be distinct, in that it uses a podcast to distribute the knowledge before the research is published. This was chosen to enable potential academic writers to be able to use the knowledge as soon as distribution is possible. The subsequent synthesis of results is, of course, relevant to the same audience, but the method enables knowledge to be transferred as soon as possible as opposed to being delayed by the process of the research itself (data collection, data synthesis, data analysis, manuscript preparation, review, and publication).

A qualitative design was chosen, as there is currently no knowledge on what specific talents, competencies, or skills leads to being particularly productive in scientific article writing. Without any knowledge on that, hypotheses cannot be made and thus a quantitative design is less suitable.

Semistructured interviews are used, as they enable a certain amount of deviation from the script, if new knowledge arises and need to be explored. At the same time, the semi-structured format ensures consistent coverage of key themes, while allowing flexibility to reach data saturation.

4.2 Study Setting and Participants

Purposive sampling will be used to identify and contact researchers relevant for the project. Researchers within health care will be selected, as health care is the most productive field of research within the University of Southern Denmark (SDU). The SDU was chosen due to the limited resources within this project.

Researchers were contacted on the basis of their number of a list of “most relevant researchers” identified through the SDU website. As a suffix to each name, a parenthesis states a number. The number is not explained on the website, but one can assume it is the number of scientific articles, the person has published so far. Researchers were contacted using the email template provided in appendix 1. In cases, where the researcher was familiar to the author of this article, a brief personal introduction was made. The specific emails can be retrieved through contact to the author.

Emails were sent in batches of three. If there was no reply within three weeks, one reminder was sent.

Criteria for inclusion:

- Researcher within the field of health care
- Being on the list of most relevant researchers
- Willing to participate
- Able to meet in person for the interview
- Sign informed consent

4.3 Data Collection Methods

Participants:

The list of potential participants was drawn from the SDU webpage, subsection Find researcher, selected publications: “Journal article”, and selected output: “Most relevant authors” at December 8th 2024, including the following names and numbers:

Most Relevant Authors			CLOSE
<input type="checkbox"/> Kaare Christensen (808)	<input type="checkbox"/> Kannan Govindan (370)	<input type="checkbox"/> Per Aagaard (326)	<input type="checkbox"/> Marianne Andersen (292)
<input type="checkbox"/> Christian Gluud (800)	<input type="checkbox"/> Philippe Grandjean (367)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carsten Bindslev-Jensen (319)	<input type="checkbox"/> Kim Brøsen (291)
<input type="checkbox"/> Sergey I. Bozhevolnyi (506)	<input type="checkbox"/> Anton Pottegård (367)	<input type="checkbox"/> Christian Ritz (318)	<input type="checkbox"/> Karen Søgaard (290)
<input type="checkbox"/> Robin Christensen (487)	<input type="checkbox"/> Niels Qvist (352)	<input type="checkbox"/> Moustapha Kassem (312)	<input type="checkbox"/> N. Asger Mortensen (290)
<input type="checkbox"/> Klaus Ejner Andersen (478)	<input type="checkbox"/> Jes Sanddal Lindholt (351)	<input type="checkbox"/> Jan Harvigsen (309)	<input type="checkbox"/> Francois Pouwer (288)
<input type="checkbox"/> Ask Elklit (454)	<input type="checkbox"/> Kirsten Kyvik (346)	<input type="checkbox"/> Jacob Eifer Møller (305)	<input type="checkbox"/> Court Pedersen (287)
<input type="checkbox"/> Jens Søndergaard (442)	<input type="checkbox"/> Ewa Maria Roos (346)	<input type="checkbox"/> Lau Caspar Thygesen (304)	<input type="checkbox"/> Horst-Gunter Rubahn (287)
<input type="checkbox"/> Jesper Hallas (441)	<input type="checkbox"/> Anette Bygum (345)	<input type="checkbox"/> Lisette Okkels Jensen (304)	<input type="checkbox"/> Hans Jørn Kolmos (283)
<input type="checkbox"/> Peter Krstrup (398)	<input type="checkbox"/> Poul Høilund-Carlson (344)	<input type="checkbox"/> Ole Nørregaard Jensen (301)	<input type="checkbox"/> Susanne S. Pedersen (282)
<input type="checkbox"/> Jørgen Jespersen (390)	<input type="checkbox"/> Martin Tepel (342)	<input type="checkbox"/> Sören Möller (297)	<input type="checkbox"/> Francesco Sannino (281)
<input type="checkbox"/> Laszlo Hegedus (387)	<input type="checkbox"/> Ove Schaffalitzky (338)	<input type="checkbox"/> Oke Gerke (295)	<input type="checkbox"/> Nikos Ntoumanis (280)
<input type="checkbox"/> Yogendra Kumar Mishra (387)	<input type="checkbox"/> Jørgen Vestbo (338)	<input type="checkbox"/> Peter Aaby (295)	<input type="checkbox"/> Janus Christian Jakobsen (278)
	<input type="checkbox"/> Jens Flensted Lassen (334)	<input type="checkbox"/> Peter Roepstorff (293)	

The list of authors was randomised prior to inviting researchers. The first batch of 25 researchers were identified first, to be able to adjust according to acceptance rate.

Interview guide:

The interview guide was developed on the basis of prespecified relevant aspects of article writing, i.e. strategies, challenges, and personal experiences.

Interviews:

Interviews will be done in person, when possible, and arranged to take place in the office of the researcher/subject. The interview will be recorded in the programme Audacity (<https://www.audacityteam.org/>), and only coughs, sneezes and toilet breaks will be cut from the original sound. There will be slight manipulation of the sound to make it suitable for podcast, but otherwise the conversation will stay unchanged for publication as podcast. Each interview is estimated to last 45 - 60 minutes.

Transcription will be conducted automatically through the use of free software, and reviewed by the author.

4.4 Data Analysis

The transcriptions will subsequently be analysed through thematic analysis, identifying codes, subthemes, and themes, which will be presented graphically in a code tree (Braun, V & Clarke, V , 2006).

No software will be used for the coding process, due to the license prices.

When the analysis has identified themes, the researchers will be invited to provide feedback on the analysis in order to make sure, the points made are reflecting their initial opinions.

4.5 Ethical Considerations

There are no sensitive data in the data collection, and consequently the informed consent process is limited to:

1. Invitation to participate through email, including a phone number, in case of questions (consent form will be attached)
2. The consent form will be presented and signed at the meeting on the day of podcast/interview recording
3. Consent forms will be kept in an electronic copy, in a locked folder

Confidentiality is not an option, as the interview will state name and number of articles written. This is information, which is accessible through public websites.

No ethical approval is necessary for this project, as no sensitive data is used or stored (<https://komite.regionsyddanmark.dk/>).

The informed consent will be used although the problem with confidentiality is limited, but to ensure that researchers/subjects feel confident that they are able to withdraw from the project. Furthermore, prior to publishing any audio, the researchers will be provided with a personal link to their own interview, which they can then review and have anything deleted that they feel like. There will be a one-week notice to review, and if they do not provide feed-back, the audio will be published in the podcast feed.

5. Validity and Reliability

Member checking will be the strategy to enhance internal validity. The publication of interviews (thick description) contributes further to the internal and external validity of the study, as anybody listening will be able to review the analyses and conclusions, as the data is available.

An audit trail will be kept, and made publicly available alongside the final manuscript.

Limitations:

- SDU was the only university selected. Due to external validity issues, it would have been advantageous to choose several universities, as well as multiple fields of research as opposed to limited to health care
- Only people who were able to meet in person were eligible for the study. This was a consequence of bilateral podcast production, as this requires a certain level of sound quality. This limitation means that only people not travelling during the period of data collection will be able to participate.
- Inter-coding reliability could have been explored, had more researchers participated in the project. But due to limited resources, this project had one researcher assigned only. Researcher bias is, however, limited due to the publication of podcasts

6. Expected Outcomes

Hopefully, the study planned will enable other authors to learn more effective manuscript writing and publication. This includes overcoming writer's block and other challenging aspects. Also, the project will be able to contribute to future tools or workshops for coming academic authors

7. Timeline

Study preparation, including protocol, informed consent, etc.	December 2024
Recruitment and recording of interviews	January - June 2025
Publication of interviews	January - June 2025
Analyses	June - October 2025
Manuscript writing	June - October 2025
Publication	October 2025
Evaluation of podcasting in research	November 2025 - January 2026

8. References

Braun, Virginia & Clarke, Victoria. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*. 3. 77-101. 10.1191/1478088706qp063oa.

De videnskabetiske Komitéer for Region Syddanmark. (2024.12.19). Komite Region Syddanmark. <https://komite.regionyddanmark.dk/>

Ericsson, Karl, Krampe, Ralf & Tesch-Roemer, Clemens. (1993). The Role of Deliberate Practice in the Acquisition of Expert Performance. *Psychological Review*. 100. 363-406. 10.1037//0033-295X.100.3.363.

Lee, Alison & Kamler, Barbara. (2008). Bringing pedagogy to doctoral publishing. *Teaching in Higher Education - TEACH HIGH EDUC*. 13. 511-523. 10.1080/13562510802334723.

Mchugh, Siobhan. (2016). How podcasting is changing the audio storytelling genre. The Radio Journal – International Studies in Broadcast & Audio Media. 14. 65-82.
10.1386/rajo.14.1.65_1.

9. Budget

Salary: 100.000 DKK
Publication fee: 30.000 DKK

10. Appendices

Appendix 1: Email to researchers

Emne: Invitation til interview om produktiv artikelskrivning

Kære [forskerens navn],

(English version below)

Jeg kontakter dig i forbindelse med et forskningsprojekt, der undersøger, hvordan højproduktive forskere arbejder med at skrive videnskabelige artikler. Formålet med projektet er at identificere de metoder og strategier, som succesfulde forskere anvender, og dele denne viden med både forskningsverdenen og en bredere akademisk lytterskare.

Den første del af projektet består af kvalitative interviews med forskere som dig, hvor samtalerne udgives som podcasts. Dette format gør det muligt at dele viden hurtigt og åbent, mens det samtidig fungerer som dataindsamling til projektet. Jeg står for interviewene, hvilket naturligvis medfører en vis forskerbias, men podcastformatet sikrer gennemsigtighed, da lytterne selv kan høre dine ord direkte og uden væsentlige redigeringer.

På Syddansk Universitets hjemmeside har jeg fundet en liste over "mest relevante forskere", hvor du er rangeret som nr. [xx]. Det fremgår, at denne relevans er baseret på antallet af publikationer – og din placering gør dig til en oplagt kandidat til at bidrage med værdifulde indsigter til projektet.

Jeg vil derfor høre, om du har mulighed for at afsætte cirka én time til en samtale med mig, hvor vi taler om dine erfaringer og bedste råd til at opnå en høj forskningsproduktion. Interviewet vil foregå i en afslappet atmosfære og med fokus på dine erfaringer og perspektiver.

Efter samtalen vil jeg sende dig et privat link til podcastudkastet, så du kan lytte det igennem og anmode om ændringer eller helt trække dit samtykke tilbage, hvis du ønsker det.

Jeg har vedhæftet en samtykkeerklæring og en kort protokol for projektet, som du kan gennemgå.

Jeg ser frem til at høre fra dig og håber, du har lyst til at deltage i projektet. Hvis du har spørgsmål, er du velkommen til at spørge pr. mail eller ringe til 6055 4498. Hvis du allerede er klar til at lave en aftale, kan du booke direkte på <https://calendly.com/akdyr vig/30min>

Med venlig hilsen,
Anne-Kirstine Dyrvig Sant, Ph.d.

telefon: 60554498

e-mail: akdyrvig@gmail.com

web: www.publipro.dk

protokol: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14539688>

PS. Jeg vil tillade mig at sende en reminder på email om 1-2 uger. Hvis du ikke besvarer hverken denne mail, eller den kommende, hører du ikke yderligere fra mig i denne forbindelse

English version:

Dear [researcher's name],

I am reaching out to you regarding a research project that examines how highly productive researchers approach writing scientific articles. The aim of the project is to identify the methods and strategies employed by successful researchers and share this knowledge with the research community and a broader academic audience.

The first part of the project consists of qualitative interviews with researchers like you, with the conversations being published as podcasts. This format allows for rapid and open knowledge sharing while simultaneously serving as data collection for the project. I will conduct the interviews, which naturally introduces some researcher bias, but the podcast format ensures transparency since listeners can hear your words directly and with minimal editing.

On the University of Southern Denmark's website, I found a list of "most relevant researchers," where you are ranked as number [xx]. This relevance appears to be based on the number of publications, and your ranking makes you an ideal candidate to provide valuable insights for the project.

I would like to ask if you would be willing to set aside approximately one hour for a conversation with me to discuss your experiences and best advice for achieving high research productivity. The interview will take place in a relaxed setting and focus on your experiences and perspectives.

After the conversation, I will send you a private link to the podcast draft so that you can listen to it and request changes or completely withdraw your consent if you wish.

I have attached a consent form and a short project protocol for you to review.

I look forward to hearing from you and hope you are interested in participating in the project. If you have any questions, please feel free to email me or call me at +45 6055 4498. If you are ready to schedule a time, you can book directly at <https://calendly.com/akdyrvig/30min>.

Best regards,

Anne-Kirstine Dyrvig Sant, Ph.D.

Phone: +45 60554498

Email: akdyrvig@gmail.com

Web: www.publipro.dk

Protocol: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14539688>

P.S. I will send a reminder email in 1-2 weeks. If I do not hear back from you regarding this email or the follow-up, you will not receive further communication from me on this matter.

Appendix 2: Interview guide

Før optagelse og rammer

1. Introduktion til Interviewet

- Formålet med interviewet er at forstå, hvilke metoder og strategier højproduktive forskere bruger til at skrive videnskabelige artikler.
- Interviewet vil blive udgivet som podcast, transskriberet, analyseret i en tematisk analyse og kan indgå i en videnskabelig artikel.

2. Praktiske Rammer

- Format: Semistruktureret interview
- Varighed: højst 90 minutter, inklusive tid til at sætte udstyr op, så der er en time til optagelse
- Sted: Fysisk møde, hvor det passer forskeren bedst - på et kontor eller i et mødelokale på et praktisk sted for forskeren
- Optagelse: Interviewet har karakter af en samtale, men med fokus på forskeren og vedkommendes erfaringer og gode råd
- Redigering: host, nys og eventuelle pauser pga. forstyrrelser klippes ud. Efterfølgende får forskeren et personligt link, hvor vedkommende kan lytte udsendelsen igennem. Hvis der er noget, forskeren ønsker fjernet, bliver det klippet ud og vil efterfølgende ikke indgå i hverken podcast eller analyse
- Samtykke: I forbindelse med interviewet underskrives informeret samtykke. Samtykke kan til enhver tid trækkes tilbage, hvorefter podcastafsnittet vil blive fjernet, og interviewet vil blive fjernet fra analysen, hvis artiklen ikke er udgivet. Hvis artiklen er udgivet, vil data ikke kunne trækkes tilbage, men de anvendes alene i anonymiseret form i artiklen.

Under optagelse

Indledning

- *"Tak fordi du vil deltage i dette interview. Formålet med projektet er at undersøge, hvordan højproduktive forskere arbejder med videnskabelige artikler, så vi kan dele erfaringer og strategier med andre forskere."*
- Introduktion til forskeren:
"Du har været forfatter eller medforfatter på X artikler, og din første artikel blev

udgivet i ÅÅÅÅ. I gennemsnit skriver du ZZ artikler om året. I dag vil vi gerne høre om dine erfaringer."

Overordnede Temaer og Spørgsmål

1. Produktivitet i Videnskabelig Artikelskrivning

1.1 Hvordan definerer du succes i videnskabelig skrivning?

(evt. uddybende spørgsmål:

- Er det i sig selv en kvalitet at være produktiv (at skrive mange artikler)? Hvorfor/hvorfor ikke?)

2. Strategier og Metoder

2.1 Hvad er dit bedste tip til at skrive mange artikler? (struktur på arbejdsdagen, skriverutiner)

2.2 Hvordan planlægger/starter du typisk en artikel? Har du en fast metode?

2.3 Hvilken rolle spiller samarbejde i artikelskrivningen for dig?

(evt. uddybende spørgsmål:

- Hvordan afslutter du en artikel og gør den klar til submission?
- Er der nogle specifikke skabeloner eller værktøjer, du bruger? (fx referenceprogrammer)
- Hvordan vælger du hvem, du vil skrive med?)

3. Udfordringer og Barrierer

3.1 Hvad er det mest udfordrende ved at skrive artikler, og hvordan håndterer du det?

(evt. uddybende spørgsmål:

- Hvad finder du lettest ved at skrive artikler? Hvorfor?
- Hvordan overkommer du mentale barrierer, som fx følelsen af at skulle bruge en hel dag uden møder for at kunne skrive?)

4. Erfaringer og Råd

4.1 Hvad ville du ønske, du havde vidst om at skrive artikler, da du startede din karriere?

(evt. uddybende spørgsmål:

- Har du artikler eller idéer, som aldrig er blevet færdiggjort? Hvorfor?
- Er der nogle ressourcer (bøger, kurser, artikler), som har hjulpet dig med at forbedre din skriveproces?
- Vil du fortælle om den bedste skriveproces, du har haft?
- Hvilken artikel har været den sjoveste eller mest givende at skrive, og hvorfor?
- Har du selv haft en mentor, du har lært fra?
- Hvad er det vigtigste, du har lært i din karriere som forsker?
- Hvilket råd ville du give til dig selv før din første artikel?)

Afsluttende temaer, som udelukkende berøres, hvis der er tid

5. Studiemetoder og Praktiske Aspekter

- *Er der bestemte studiedesigns, som gør det lettere at skrive artikler?*
- *Hvordan finder du finansiering til dine projekter og artikler?*
- *Hvordan vælger du tidsskrifter?*

6. Kreativitet, idéer og fremtid

- *Hvordan får du idéer til nye artikler? Har du en specifik proces?*
- *Hvornår ved du, at en idé skal opgives?*
- *Hvad motiverer dig til at skrive artikler?*
- *Hvordan ser du fremtiden for videnskabelig skrivning og publikation?*

7. Køn og Produktivitet

- *Hvorfor tror du, at den første kvinde på listen først er placeret som nr. 18?
(Valgfrit, hvis det er relevant i konteksten.)*

Appendix 3: Consent form

Consent form for participation in Danish

Tilpasset fra DET VIDENSKABSETISKE KOMITÉSYSTEM

(S1)

Informeret samtykke til deltagelse i et forskningsprojekt.

Forskningsprojektets titel: SPEAC – Sharing Perspectives on Effective Academic Communication

Erklæring fra forsøgspersonen:

Jeg har fået skriftlig og mundtlig information og jeg ved nok om formål, metode, fordele og ulemper til at sige ja til at deltage.

Jeg ved, at det er frivilligt at deltage, og at jeg altid kan trække mit samtykke tilbage uden at miste mine nuværende eller fremtidige rettigheder til behandling.

Jeg giver samtykke til, at deltage i forskningsprojektet, og har fået en kopi af dette samtykkeark samt en kopi af den skriftlige information om projektet til eget brug.

Forsøgspersonens navn: _____

Dato: _____ Underskrift: _____

Ønsker du at blive informeret om forskningsprojektets resultat samt eventuelle konsekvenser for dig?:

Ja _____ (sæt x) Nej _____ (sæt x)

Samtykke til anvendelse af klip fra interviews i markedsføringsmateriale

Jeg giver hermed tilladelse til, at klip fra interviews, som jeg har deltaget i og godkendt, må anvendes i markedsføringsmateriale for forskningsprojektet SPEAC og øvrige aktiviteter i Publipro, herunder på hjemmesider, i præsentationer og på sociale medier.

Jeg er informeret om, at jeg til enhver tid kan trække dette samtykke tilbage, uden at det påvirker min deltagelse i forskningsprojektet eller mine øvrige rettigheder.

Ja _____ (sæt x) Nej _____ (sæt x)

Dato: _____ Underskrift: _____

Erklæring fra den, der afgiver information:

Jeg erklærer, at forsøgspersonen har modtaget mundtlig og skriftlig information om forsøget.

Efter min overbevisning er der givet tilstrækkelig information til, at der kan træffes beslutning om deltagelse i forsøget.

Navnet på den, der har afgivet information:

Dato: _____ Underskrift: _____

Projektidentifikation: (Zenodo DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14539688>)

Consent form for participation in English

Tilpasset fra DET VIDENSKABSETISKE KOMITÉSYSTEM

Informed Consent for Participation in a Research Project

Title of the Research Project: SPEAC – Sharing Perspectives on Effective Academic Communication

Declaration by the Participant:

I have received both written and oral information, and I have sufficient knowledge about the purpose, methods, benefits, and disadvantages to agree to participate.

I understand that participation is voluntary, and I can withdraw my consent at any time without losing my current or future rights to care or treatment.

I give my consent to participate in the research project and have received a copy of this consent form as well as a copy of the written information about the project for my own use.

Participant's Name: _____

Date: _____ **Signature:** _____

Would you like to be informed about the research project's results and any implications for you?

Yes _____ (tick box) No _____ (tick box)

Consent to Use Clips from Interviews in Marketing Materials

I hereby consent to the use of clips from interviews in which I have participated and approved for marketing materials related to the SPEAC research project and other activities under Publipro, including websites, presentations, and social media.

I understand that I can withdraw this consent at any time without it affecting my participation in the research project or my other rights.

Yes _____ (tick box) No _____ (tick box)

Date: _____ **Signature:** _____

Declaration by the Person Providing the Information:

I declare that the participant has received both oral and written information about the study.

To the best of my knowledge, sufficient information has been provided for the participant to make an informed decision about participation in the study.

Name of the Person Providing the Information:

Date: _____ **Signature:** _____

Project Identification: (Zenodo DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14539688>)

Samtykke til behandling af personoplysninger

Formål med behandling af personoplysninger:

Som en del af forskningsprojektet **SPEAC – Sharing Perspectives on Effective Academic Communication** indsamles og behandles personoplysninger for at kunne gennemføre projektet i overensstemmelse med dets formål.

De personoplysninger, der indsamles, omfatter:

- Navn, kontaktoplysninger og underskrift
- Optagelser og eventuelle transkriptioner fra interviews
- Anden relevant information, som du vælger at dele under projektet.

Behandlingen sker i henhold til gældende databeskyttelseslovgivning, herunder EU's databeskyttelsesforordning (GDPR).

Dine rettigheder:

- Du har ret til at få indsigt i de oplysninger, der behandles om dig
- Du har ret til at få urigtige oplysninger rettet
- Du har ret til at få dine oplysninger slettet, medmindre behandlingen er nødvendig for at opfylde juridiske eller forskningsmæssige forpligtelser
- Du har ret til at trække dit samtykke tilbage til enhver tid uden at det påvirker din deltagelse i projektet eller dine øvrige rettigheder.

Samtykkeerklæring:

Jeg giver hermed tilladelse til, at mine personoplysninger indsamles, opbevares og behandles som led i forskningsprojektet SPEAC og i forbindelse med markedsføringsmateriale, hvis jeg har givet separat samtykke hertil.

Jeg er blevet informeret om formålet med behandlingen og mine rettigheder som registreret person.

Forsøgspersonens navn: _____

Dato: _____

Underskrift: _____

Kontaktoplysninger for dataansvarlig:

Navn: Publipro

CVR: 34992037

Kontaktperson: Anne-Kirstine Dyrvig Sant

E-mail: akdyrvig@gmail.com

Telefon: 60554498

Consent for the Processing of Personal Data

Purpose of Processing Personal Data:

As part of the research project **SPEAC – Sharing Perspectives on Effective Academic Communication**, personal data is collected and processed to conduct the project in accordance with its objectives.

The personal data collected include:

- Name, contact information, and signature
- Recordings and any transcriptions from interviews
- Other relevant information that you choose to share during the project.

The processing of personal data will comply with applicable data protection laws, including the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Your Rights:

- You have the right to access the information processed about you
- You have the right to have incorrect information corrected
- You have the right to have your data deleted unless the processing is necessary to fulfill legal or research-related obligations
- You have the right to withdraw your consent at any time without affecting your participation in the project or your other rights.

Consent Declaration:

I hereby consent to the collection, storage, and processing of my personal data as part of the SPEAC research project and, where applicable, for marketing materials if I have provided separate consent for this purpose.

I have been informed of the purpose of the processing and my rights as a data subject.

Participant's Name: _____

Date: _____

Signature: _____

Contact Information for Data Controller:

Name: Publipro

CVR: 34992037

Contact Person: Anne-Kirstine Dyrvig Sant

Email: akdyrvig@gmail.com

Phone: 60554498

Appendix 4: Changes to this document

2024.12.21: Update to version 1.1:

- Registration with Zenodo.org at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14539688>
- Addition of protocol DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14539688> to this document, and to the email to researchers invited.
- Addition to methods: Randomisation of the list of researchers when inviting

2024.12.28: Update to version 1.2:

- Change of the sentence in section Før optagelse under Interview guide in Appendix 2: "*skrevet X artikler, været medforfatter på Y*" was changed to "har været forfatter eller medforfatter på x artikler"
- Change to email invitation to include link for booking, adding these sentences: Hvis du har spørgsmål, er du velkommen til at spørge pr. mail eller ringe til 6055 4498. Hvis du allerede er klar til at lave en aftale, kan du booke direkte på <https://calendly.com/akdyrvig/30min>

2024.12.30: Update to version 1.3:

- Email written in Danish and English translation, as some researcher might not read/speak Danish
- Decision to introduce two invitation steps, and invite only the top 25, until acceptance rate is known, adding this sentence to section 4.3: "The first batch of 25 researchers were identified first, to be able to adjust according to acceptance rate."
- Consent form updated with protocol DOI + consent to use interview clips in marketing, and consent form in English